

**PREVALENCE OF RED CELL ALLOIMMUNIZATION IN REPEATEDLY
TRANSFUSED PATIENTS WITH B- THALASSEMIA IN SOLAPUR DISTRICT,
MAHARASHTRA STATE, INDIA.**

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Abstract :

β -major-thalassemia is a congenital hemolytic anemia caused by defects in β -globin chain synthesis. The globin chain that is produced in excess is responsible for the ineffective erythropoiesis and shortened red blood cell (RBC) survival. The present study includes the prevalence of red cell alloimmunization in repeatedly transfused patients with β -Thalassemia in Solapur District, Maharashtra, India. A cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted over one year period from January 2010 to December 2010 at Smt. Gopabai Damani Blood Bank (Indian Red Cross Society) Solapur, Maharashtra, India. A total of 74 Thalassemia patients receiving multiple blood transfusions at intervals of 2 to 4 weeks, or who had received at least 20 transfusions, were included in this study. The diagnosis of Thalassemia was confirmed by patient's standard hemoglobin electrophoresis Reports Clinical transfusion records of 74 Thalassemia patients who fulfilled the criteria were analyzed for the presence of alloimmunization, their antibody specificity and the time interval of RBC immunization from start of transfusion. Ethnic background, status of splenectomy, age at start of transfusion and the number of blood units received were also recorded.

Laboratory investigations using standard blood bank methods, serum was analyzed prior to each transfusion to detect new antibodies to RBC antigens. All pre transfusion sera were also tested to determine their phenotype for the following blood group systems: ABO; Rhesus (D, C, E, c, and e); Kell (K, k), Kidd (Kpa, Kpb) and Duffy (Fya, Fyb). Clinical and laboratory data were collected and analyzed to find out the frequency, pattern and factors influencing red cell immunization secondary to multiple blood transfusions in these patients.

Introduction:

Alloimmunity is a condition in which the body gains immunity, from another individual of the same species, against the foreign cells. Antibodies must be identified in the recipient's serum before each transfusion so that compatible blood can be provided. Several factors might have contributed to this finding, such as the heterogeneity of the population, the difference in the number of studied patients, the differences in age at first transfusion, antigenic differences between the blood donor and the recipient; the recipient's immune status; and immunomodulatory effects of the allogenic blood transfusions on the recipient's immune system and splenectomy. In 1989 Walker *et al.*, pointed out the Alloimmunization by blood transfusion. Sirchia *et al.*, (1995)

studied the Red cell alloantibodies in thalassemia major patients. Blumberg and Gettings (2003) find out that the WBC reduction of RBC transfusions is associated with decreased incidence of RBC alloimmunization. With the growing knowledge of the immune effects of current blood transfusions and limited data on the immune status of Thalassemia patients, a large study addressing the complex interaction of these factors is needed. Khalid Hassan and coauthors were found out the red cell alloimmunization in repeatedly transfused Thalassemia Major Patients in Pakistan. Red cell alloimmunization in routinely transfused patients of beta thalassemia major was studied by Gupta *et al.*, (2010). The present study was undertaken to estimate the incidence of allo-immunization in multiply transfused thalasseemics and to evaluate factors which may influence the development of antibodies

Material and Methods:

A cross-sectional descriptive study of antibody screening was conducted over one year period from January 2010 to December 2010 at Smt. Gopabai Damani Blood Bank (Indian Red Cross Society) Solapur, Maharashtra, India.

All pretransfusion sera were also tested to determine their phenotype for the following blood group systems: ABO; Rhesus (D, C, E, c, and e); Kell (K, k), Kidd (Kpa, Kpb) and Duffy (Fya, An antigen panel was used for the antibody screening procedure, where the serum was mixed with saline suspended red cells in LISS Coombs gel card incubated at 37°C for 15 minutes. Antibody screening at 4°C, 22°C and 37°C was carried out in a saline phase, by indirect antiglobulin technique (IAT), using papain cystein, low ionic strength solution (LISS) and polyethylene glycol (PEG).

Results:

A total of 74 patients were included in the study. 31 (31.82 %) patients were females and 43 (22.94%) males. The age of patients was ranged from 3 to 18 years. They had regular blood transfusions during periods ranging from 3 to 18 years. The interval between blood transfusions was 18-30 days.

Present study investigated 74 cases of multiply transfused thalassemia major patients for development of alloantibodies against red cells by indirect antiglobulin test, using 3-red cell panel, and when required 11-red cell panel. Anti-red cell alloantibodies were detected in 01 (0.74) patients, in male 01 (0.43%) and in female 00 (0.00%) patients. Demographic data of alloimmunization patients have been shown in table 1. The results shows that the prevalence percent of splenectomy in males 04 (1.72%) and in females 03 (0.93). All 74 patients with alloimmunization were treated with prednisone, intravenous immunoglobulin and cyclosporine A. Beside the above drugs; azathioprine was used for three of them.

Table-1 Sex specific red cell alloimmunization positivity prevalence percentage

Sex	Total No.	Thalassemia Major (%)	Thalassemia Intermediate (%)	Thalassemia Minor (%)	Splenectomy (Prevalence %)	Red cell alloimmunization (Prevalence %)
Male	43	25 (10.75)	13 (5.59)	05 (2.15)	04 (1.72)	01 (0.43)
Female	31	21(6.51)	06 (1.86)	04 (1.24)	03 (0.93)	00 (0.00)
Patients (Male + Female)	74	46 (30.04)	19 (14.06)	09 (6.66)	07 (5.18)	01 (0.74)

Discussion:

This is a study about red cell alloimmunization rate among β -major-Thalassemia patients on regular blood transfusion. Post-storage leukodepleted blood was used for transfusion. It is not a standard practice in our center to give phenotype-matched red cells to patients with thalassemia. The use of phenotypematched blood is given only in patients who have developed alloantibodies. Red blood cell alloimmunization was found in 01 (0.74) patients. Our patients were treated with immunosuppressive drugs including prednisone, intravenous immunoglobulin, cyclosporine A and azathioprine and now all of them are in healthy condition. Khalid Hassan *et al.* (2004) observed that the Red cell alloimmunization in repeatedly transfused Thalassemia Major patients in Pakistan, in British Thompson *et al.* (2011) studied the Red cell alloimmunization in a diverse population of transfused patients with thalassaemia. Walker *et al.* (1989) observed the alloimmunization following blood transfusion. These observations on Red cell alloimmunization are an important finding in patients with β -major-Thalassemia. Thalassemia major patients managed by regular transfusion regimen may develop anti-red cell alloimmunization. If the alloantibodies are hemolyzing in nature, transfusion reaction may occur, and provision of blood thereafter requires matching of the relevant blood group in addition to 'ABO' and Rh 'D' matching. The hemolyzing nature of antibodies should be determined in patients who develop these antibodies, and transfusion should be arranged accordingly. Data regarding the impact of platelet refractoriness on morbidity and mortality for thrombocytopenic patients are inconsistent. Failure to achieve platelet counts greater than $5 \times 10^9/L$ significantly increases the probability of life-threatening bleeding. The rate of red blood cell alloimmunization is relatively low in our patients. The age at first blood transfusion and splenectomy were not statistically significant as risk factors for alloimmunization in this study.

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